

Working Paper: Implementing Generative AI in the Historical Studies

Sarah Oberbichler*[❖], Cindarella Petz*[✧]

DH Lab, Leibniz Institute of European History

(*These authors contributed equally to this work)

❖oberbichler@ieg-mainz.de; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1031-2759>

✧petz@ieg-mainz.de; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6178-7332>

(Version: February 2025)

Abstract

This working paper provides a detailed overview on implementation strategies, critical evaluation, and best practices to use generative AI for research and analysis in historical studies. It distinguishes between two key applications of AI in historical research: as a supplementary tool and as a methodological component. The paper further emphasizes a responsible, purposeful, and demand-oriented approach with generative AI, which is guided by the principle of minimal computing. It outlines various application scenarios and provides clear frameworks for evaluating when and how to implement AI technology, addressing both individual and institutional responsibilities in order to maintain scientific integrity and adherence to data security and privacy. The aim is to maximize research impact and to maintain space for creative exploration and breakthrough innovation, while balancing performance and reliability needs with ethical considerations and sustainability.

This working paper builds upon the reader's basic understanding of how Large Language Models (LLMs) work in general, and focuses on providing practical guidance for researchers, who plan to integrate AI technology into their historical research but face uncertainties about implementation, critical evaluation, and best practices. Key aspects covered in this working paper include:

- Assessment of the usage of generative AI as tools versus methodological applications (with application scenarios).
- Risk assessment frameworks covering legal, ethical, and environmental aspects, focusing on scientific integrity, input evaluation, and reflection of outputs.
- Recommendations for a responsible use of AI technology.
- Recommendations for different implementation levels and types of models.

Acknowledgements: We want to express our thanks for the discussion of this paper at the working group Digitality at the Leibniz Institute of European History (IEG), and the feedback rounds with Fabian Cremer and Thorsten Wübbena (in alphabetic order).

Content Table

Abstract	1
AI as Tool or as a Method?	3
Fluidity of AI as a Tool and as a Method.....	3
Research-based Application Scenarios for Generative AI.....	4
Using AI More Likely as a Tool.....	4
Using AI More Likely as a Method	5
Individual and Institutional Responsibilities	6
When Using AI as a Tool	6
When Using AI as a Method.....	6
Common Ground at the DH Lab at IEG Mainz.....	6
What You Need to Know Before to Start?	7
Overall Questions to Ask.....	7
Risk Assessment	7
Key Concept: Minimal Computing in AI Research.....	9
Taking Over Responsibility When Using AI as a Tool and as a Method.....	10
Being Transparent	10
Questioning Inputs.....	11
Evaluating Outputs	13
Recommendations for Implementation.....	15
Open-Weight, Open-Source and Closed-Source Models.....	15
Accessing Large Language Models Beyond Commercial Tools.....	16
Bibliography.....	17

AI as Tool or as a Method?

This working paper distinguishes between two implementation levels of generative AI in academic work: its use as a research support tool and its integration as a methodological component. While these classifications naturally overlap and are not always clear-cut, understanding their primary distinctions helps clarify their application and impact in research processes.

When we refer to AI as a tool, we are describing technology that supports and enhances existing research processes. This includes applications like text translation, content summary, or data organization—tasks that support rather than fundamentally alter research methodology.

In contrast, AI as a method refers to the direct integration of AI technology into the analytical framework. Here, AI becomes part of the methodological approach itself, particularly in source analysis and interpretation. This goes beyond supporting the research processes and becomes an integral part of how we understand and interpret our research materials. To increase clarity, we highlighted recommendations for using AI as a method with violet text throughout this paper.

Fluidity of AI as a Tool and as a Method

It is important to note that the distinction between tool-based and methodological AI implementation is not always clear-cut, and some applications may fall into overlapping categories. This fluidity becomes clear on the example of Optical Character Recognition (OCR):

When used as a tool, OCR might be employed to convert documents or sources into machine-searchable text to facilitate further review. When used as part of a methodology, OCR becomes the crucial first step in a systematic corpus analysis, where the accurate digitization of archival material is essential for subsequent computational text analysis, or natural language processing. The quality and characteristics of the OCR process directly influence the research results and must be considered part of the methodological framework.

Research-based Application Scenarios for Generative AI

General application scenarios in the historical studies entail the following non-exhaustive and non-ordered lists of tasks and implementation examples:

Using AI More Likely as a Tool

The following application scenarios use AI more likely supportive to their general research process:

<i>Application Scenarios</i>	<i>Implementation Examples</i>
Scientific Writing <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Spell checking• Translation support• Managing citations• Formatting of text and/or bibliography• Text improvement• Text coherence improvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Grammarly• Writefull• DeepL• ChatAI of GWDG
Literature Review <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Literature search• Text summary• Text explanation	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Elicit• ORKG Ask• Research Rabbit• Semantic Scholar
Scientific Brainstorming <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Methodology brainstorming: Weighting pro and cons of a selected research method (validity, reliability, applicability)• Brainstorming limitations: Pointing to possible limitations and constraints of a study• Brainstorming biases: Highlighting potential biases in historical sources and interpretations	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• ChatAI of GWDG (e.g., with Deepseek R1)• OpenAI Deep Research• Claude
Coding Assistance <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Finding bugs: Identifying incorrect and/or incomplete code, and offering how to improve code• Code suggestions and solutions: Improving code, and/or providing code solutions• Data visualization: Providing code for data visualization	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• ChatAI of GWDG (e.g., with Qwen 2.5 Coder 32B Instruct)• Copilot• GPT4All (has many coding models)
Data Exploration <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Checking on data completeness• Pointing to errors or unusual patterns in data	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Pandas AI

Using AI More Likely as a Method

The following application scenarios use AI more likely as central part of their research process:

<i>Application Scenarios</i>	<i>Implementation Examples</i>
<p>Natural Language Processing (NLP) Tasks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Data Cleaning: OCR post-correction, preparing data for further qualitative or quantitative analysis• Text Extraction: Extracting relevant text from digitized sources to create suitable corpora tailored to the research question• Entities Extraction: Assisting in extracting and linking entities (e.g., individuals, organizations, places) and finding relations between them• Text Classification: Supporting text classification tasks such as sentiment analysis or genre classification.• Tagging: Tagging texts with relevant categories or labels.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• HuggingFace (e.g., NuExtract for information extraction)• GWDG models via API• Ollama (e.g., Llama family models)
<p>Computer Vision</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Image Extraction: Detecting and extracting images within digitized historical sources, fastening work flows via Multimodal Large Language Models (MLLMs)• OCR: Transcribing historical documents• Image Analysis: Analyzing image composition and content via MLLMs or Large Vision Models (LVMs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• ChatAI of GWDG (e.g., OpenGVLab)• GWDG models via API• Google Cloud AI• HuggingFace Model Caracal• Detectron 2
<p>Method Development</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Model training: Developing specialized models trained on highly specific datasets.• Comparative experiments: Systematic experimentation with different models on similar tasks.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• HuggingFace• Overview in “Awesome List LLMs”

Individual and Institutional Responsibilities

Responsible AI Integration in historical research requires both thorough understanding of source materials and AI expertise. These requirements manifest at individual and institutional levels, creating a framework for effective implementation.

When Using AI as a Tool

At the individual level, researchers using AI as a supporting tool need basic AI literacy to effectively utilize these technologies while maintaining critical awareness of their limitations. While user-friendly AI tools make routine tasks more accessible, researchers must still exercise careful judgment about their appropriate application and potential impacts on research outcomes.

At the institutional level, important requirements are clear guidelines for tool selection, data security protocols, and ethical considerations specific to AI-assisted research tools. This includes support for commonly used AI applications while maintaining research integrity.

When Using AI as a Method

At the individual level, researchers are responsible to develop deeper technical expertise and/or to establish substantial collaborations with AI specialists. This requires understanding not just how to use AI, but how it fundamentally affects research design, data analysis, and interpretation of results.

At the institutional level, key requirements are clear guidelines that prioritizes data security and ethical AI usage as well as recommendations on how to get the needed technical infrastructure.

Common Ground at the DH Lab at IEG Mainz

At IEG Mainz, collaboration between domain experts and technical specialists has led to a robust environment for methodological innovation. Both approaches, AI as a tool or a method, benefit from the DH Lab's collaborative framework within the IEG, which brings together domain expertise and technical knowledge. As methodological best practices for implementing LLMs in historical research continue to emerge, this integrated approach provides a strong foundation for developing robust research standards while maintaining scholarly rigor.

Through meaningful exchange and clear guidelines, researchers can effectively navigate both technical and methodological complexities, whether using AI as a supplementary tool or as a core research method.

What You Need to Know Before to Start?

Overall Questions to Ask

Before using AI technology as a tool (or method), we recommend to ask yourself key questions that should help create awareness of both capabilities and limitations while developing the practical skills needed to integrate AI technology into your own research agenda or research methodology:

Fig. 1: Questions to ask before considering the use of generative AI for research (Image: S. Oberbichler & C. Petz 2025). The violet text refers to questions relevant when using AI as a method.

Risk Assessment

To ensure optimal results, we need to balance performance, stability, legal and ethical concerns and ecological costs. This means, too, if other less cost-intensive methods than LLMs would provide similar performances, these should be favored following the idea of minimal computing.¹ However, low technical hurdles and project time restraints do not replace the necessary reflection on the technology itself as part of good research practice.

While [EU AI Act](#) outlines regulations for safe AI usage, it has restricted applicability for the historical studies, but still provides a great starting point for reflection. In order to evaluate whether to use a LLM-based tool (or method), please assess the following risks:

¹ See Infobox on p. 10.

Societal Risks and Limits to the Safe, Recommended, or Legal Applicability of AI

Suitability: Was the tool (or model) designed for the intended application?

Legal Dimensions: Are GDPR Guidelines followed? Does usage conform to the EU AI Act? Are the sources used open-access, closed-access, licensed, and/or contain sensitive data?

This influences your decision on which tools (or models) you should use! Note, that data security and privacy concerns arise when processing prompts on third-party-owned services. There, inputs, prompts, and requests are sent to third-party-owned servers, which might not adhere to European privacy regulations.

Applicability: What are the limits to the safe, recommended, or legal applicability of AI? In the context of the historical studies, it is essential to know the limitations of using AI tools when, e.g.,:

- grading student papers
- writing peer reviews
- writing grant proposals
- reviewing grant proposals

Additional Reading: [Ghent University \(2024\): GDPR: What should I take into account when developing or using AI?](#) AND [Forschungsteam ZGKI \(2025\): EU AI ACT Kompass](#)

[Executive Committee of the DFG \(2023\): Statement on the Influence of Generative Models of Text and Image Creation on Science and the Humanities and on the DFG's Funding Activities](#)

Ecological and Economical Consequences

Immediate costs:

<i>AI as a tool</i>	<i>AI as a method</i>
Costs of using the tool (e.g., ChatGPT membership vs. free Shibboleth access to ChatAI)	Costs of using or buying model access (API), computing time access (GPU/CPU), prompt or token access, ...

Hidden costs: Which damages to the environment are related to the use of the tool (or model)?

Additional Reading: [Li et al \(2023\): Making AI Less "Thirsty": Uncovering and Addressing the Secret Water Footprint of AI Models](#) AND [Carbon Footprint Calculator for Machine Learning](#)

Centrality of LLMs in the proposed project

Necessity: Is it necessary to use a LLM-based tool (or method) for this project? Will you do systematic experiments with LLMs in this project?

Inevitability: Would alternative tools (or methods) provide similar results and with similar costs? If so, these alternative methods might be preferred to using LLM-based tools or methods. This follows the idea of minimal computing.

Key Concept: Minimal Computing in AI Research

The concept of minimal computing refers to environmentally conscious usage of AI by:

- Using LLMs selectively when they demonstrate clear performance advantages
- Conducting systematic experiments to validate necessity.
- Employing specialized, task-specific models rather than general-purpose ones.
- Using models as small as possible.

This approach optimizes computational resources while maintaining research effectiveness.

Recommended Reading: [Digital Humanities Climate Coalition \(2025\): Minimal Computing](#)

Taking Over Responsibility When Using AI as a Tool and as a Method

Using LLM-based tools or methods require the need to take over responsibility and human operational oversight by active engagement (“human-in-the-loop”) in the following steps:

Fig. 2: Reflection on steps in the AI-assisted research process (Image: S. Oberbichler & C. Petz 2025).

This ensures methodological rigor while addressing AI-specific research challenges.

Being Transparent

When incorporating AI into academic research, whether as a tool (or method), adherence to rigorous academic standards is essential. As with any research instrument or methodology, transparency about AI usage is fundamental to maintaining scholarly integrity. These measures increase the reproducibility of findings. But as LLMs are not deterministic, there are limits to this!

AI as a tool	AI as a method
Crediting which tool (and possibly which model version) was used for which kind of tasks, including which prompts if applicable.	Crediting which model of which origin was used for which kind of tasks <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reporting technical specifications: Model version, GPU, .. • Documenting model parameters, settings, portion sizes, prompt(s), ...

Additional Resources: [Leibniz Association \(2024\): Empfehlung zur Sicherung der guten wissenschaftlichen Praxis beim Umgang mit Künstlicher Intelligenz](#) AND [Oberbichler \(2024\): AI Model Research Documentation Sheet \(AIRDocS\)](#)

Questioning Inputs

When working with AI models, source criticism, data criticism, and tool (or method) criticism are very much interconnected. This means that in order to critically reflect, for example, the appropriateness or applicability of a model, it is essential to examine your data as well as the data the model was trained on for a specific task. First, we take a look at the left half of the epistemological framework as shown in Fig. 3:

Fig. 3 Epistemological framework for AI-assisted research. (Image: S. Oberbichler & C. Petz 2024).

Extending the established critical reflection of source criticism to data requires examining four key areas:

Critical reflection on source & data examines provenance, content, context, and formal aspects like data types. This includes understanding how the dataset was collected, what transformations were applied, and whether the collection methods introduced systematic errors.

Critical reflection on data biases examines inherent perspectives, mis-/representation issues, and possible discrimination. This involves examining how different groups, languages, and domains are represented in the data, identifying potentially harmful categorizations, and understanding whose perspectives are privileged or excluded in the dataset.

Critical reflection on tools and models investigates the technical implementation as well as their appropriateness. This means examining the model architecture, understanding how the tool processes and transforms data, and considering the consequences of its deployment in different contexts (applicability).

AI as a tool	AI as a method
<p>Tool criticism</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appropriateness of the tool for the intended tasks and data types: What was this tool trained on and what was it trained to do? 	<p>Model criticism:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appropriateness of the model for the intended tasks and data types: What was this model trained on and what was it trained to do? • Using specialized and as small as possible models following the principle of minimal computing in AI-based research • Assessing the influence of the training data on the results and representation

Adhering to legal considerations of data usage requires careful attention to data privacy regulations, copyright restrictions, and usage limitations when working with sensitive or private or confidential material, copyrighted content, licensed data, restricted information, including unpublished works or student submissions.

- Awareness about legal liabilities through possible violations of privacy, licenses, confidentiality, and other legal limitations of datasets used. Content uploaded (including input, prompts, requests) to Chatbots and other cloud-based AI systems can be potentially exposed to unauthorized access, commercially reused, sold, and linked with other personal or sensitive information.²
- Awareness about copyright violations through harmful prompts or predatory models: Note: Meta-analysis & summaries of copyrighted material are usually legal, but reproducing copyrighted material is a violation of the copyright. Note: In Germany, the “Wissenschaftsschranke” allows researchers to use copyrighted works for scientific purposes without needing explicit permission. This is vital for fostering academic research, as it enables access to a broader range of materials for analysis and study. However, researchers must be aware of potential conflicts between the “Wissenschaftsschranke” and licensing agreements. Generally, regulations by archives should be respected in order to allow good collaboration.

AI as a tool	AI as a method
<p>Security and privacy concerns: Awareness about legal liabilities of sensitive information and copyrighted materials when using cloud-based AI tools</p>	<p>Security and privacy concerns: Sensitive and/or copyright protected material should be processed via local models, or European-based cloud servers. Commercially used platforms should be avoided.</p>

² See also Chapter: “What do I need to know before to start?” (p. 6-7)

Additional Resources: [Markert \(v.0.1\): Entscheidungsbaum zu urheberrechtlichen Aspekten der Nutzung von Digitalisaten](#)

[Anne Burkhardt \(2025\): KI und Globale \(Un\)Gerechtigkeit: Ethische Perspektiven auf Künstliche Intelligenz](#)

[Navigli et al \(2023\): Biases in Large Language Models: Origins, Inventory, and Discussion](#) AND [Ferrer et al \(2021\). Bias and Discrimination in AI: A cross-disciplinary perspective](#) AND [Mauermann & Oberbichler \(2025\). LLM Biases: Expected and Unexpected Model Design Effects in Historical Newspaper Article Extraction on the Messina Earthquake.](#)

Evaluating Outputs

The right half of the epistemological framework (Fig. 3) concerns the output evaluation. It is recommended to critically reflect on AI tools' (or models') roles and limitations while maintaining responsibility for output verification. This includes documenting how AI systems influence our research processes, understanding tool (or model) constraints, and validating or verifying AI-generated outputs (compare to right half of Fig. 2).

- E.g., comparing generated summaries of text
- E.g., if generated code actually works as intended
- E.g., if the code works consistently well

Fig. 4: Performance Feedback Loop (Image: S. Oberbichler & C. Petz 2024)

Considering limitations of the reliability of the output includes being aware about

- replication of biases within the (tool or model training, and your own source) dataset into the results. The reflection on biases is a necessary extension of the source criticism of your own dataset.
- confabulations ('hallucinations'), when the tool (or model) is inventing 'facts'. LLMs are "stochastic parrots," this means they tend to recreate their training input with a certain probability.

AI as a tool	AI as a method
Comparison of different tools	Systematic experimentation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optimization of model parameters, settings, temperature, batches, prompts, ... • Prompt iteration & prompt engineering (“prompt criticism”) • <u>Note</u>: Strategies for prompt engineering depend on the model used • Portioning (“batches economy”)
Quality of results: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qualitative assessment of the output • Checking each step of the tool (if applicable) 	Quality of results: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluation and robustness tests of results + documentation • Explainability (“Explainable AI”) • Reliability & plausibility • In general: How good is good enough? Do you need to stop at 90% accuracy? • Balancing quality vs time resources • Performance Feedback Loop • After systematic testing, do alternative methods work similarly well or better? • If so, alternatives should be preferred following the idea of minimal computing

Recommendations for Implementation

Open-Weight, Open-Source and Closed-Source Models

LLMs exist in different sizes and accessibility and/or transparency levels. The explanations below give insight into the difference between open-weight, open-source, and closed-source models:

	<i>What is Available</i>	<i>What Can be Done</i>
<i>Open-Source Models</i>	Everything: code, training method, data	These models allow for full modification and insight into how it works. These models allow to have an insight into the data the model is trained on. They can be used locally.
<i>Open-Weight Models</i>	Just the trained model parameters	These models can be fine-tuned and adapted within limits. They can be used locally.
<i>Closed-Source Models</i>	Only the interface/API	These models are proprietary, controlled and maintained within a closed environment such as Chatbots. Access to the underlying code and training data is not possible, often making these models black boxes to external users. These models cannot be used locally.

We recommend using fully open-source models where possible, as they allow critical examination of training data and complete transparency of the model architecture. Models like [Tulu 3](#) from The Allen Institute for AI or from [LLM360](#) enable to better understand potential biases and limitations. Running these models locally also ensures that your research data, prompts, and outputs remain private and under your control.

When open-source models aren't feasible, open-weight models can provide a good alternative. Open-weight models in various sizes, such as the [Llama](#) models by Meta, can be run locally to ensure full privacy.

For cases where closed-source models such as [Google Cloud AI](#) are the best option, we recommend using APIs rather than web interfaces, as this provides more control over the interaction and better integration possibilities for research workflows. Note, that data security and privacy concerns arise when processing prompts on third-party-owned services.³ Input, prompts and requests are sent to the service, which might not adhere to European privacy regulations.

Accessing Large Language Models Beyond Commercial Tools

Large Language Models can be accessed beyond integrated components of specific research tools (like literature search engines, or translation software such as [DeepL](#)) or commercial Chatbots like [ChatGPT](#) in three main ways:

- Locally via research Chat-Interfaces or research API's for programmatic access and workflow integration.
- Through local installation on your own hardware (via chat-interfaces or programming environments).
- Through HPC clusters providing model and GPU access.

Below we list examples for each access point. While this list does not claim to be exhaustive, it should give a good overview of the available access options for researchers at the time this paper was published.

Cloud-based Research Chat-Interfaces or Research API-Access

The GWDG in Göttingen, for example, provides secure access to open-source and open-weight models in Germany. All services are hosted in academic data centers according to German data protection and data security directives.

- Their Chatbot [ChatAI](#) offers an easy and secure access to powerful generative AI. The intuitive interface allows users to chat directly with a selection of different AI models. Using your Shibboleth login credentials, the interface can be accessed free of charge.
- [API access](#) for the usage of the [models](#) in programming environments can be requested (up to 200 calls per day).

Locally Installed Chat-Interfaces

Locally installed Desktop Apps allow the usage of large language models to run privately without local data ever leaving the private device. An example is [GPT4ALL](#) by Nomic, an open-source ecosystem used for integrating LLMs into consumer hardware without paying for a platform or hardware subscription.

Model Running Platforms and Programming Environments

[Ollama](#) offers a powerful and user-friendly way to run various LLMs locally, supporting multiple models through both chat interfaces and programming environments. Ollama is an open-source project that serves as a powerful and user-friendly platform for running LLMs on your local machine.

³ Compare to chapter on Legal Dimension of Risk Analysis, p. 6-7.

[HuggingFace](#) provides comprehensive tools for model deployment:

- The Transformers library for implementing models in Python
- Model Hub for accessing and downloading thousands of models
- Specialized tools for local model optimization and deployment

[Anacondas](#) provides on-premises deployment options for LLMs, enabling researchers to securely host and utilize LLMs locally.

Note: Limited computing power may require external CPU/GPU servers (e.g., Cloud-based GPU, renting GPU server, or buying a GPU server). For example, [Google Colab Notebooks](#) offer 20 hours of free GPU per week. [GrokCloud](#) offers free API access to a specific limit.

HPC Clusters Providing Model Access

When using mid- to large-size models that require more computing power, access to High Performance Computing (HPC) clusters can be an option, where you can externalize CPU/GPU usage. Usually, access is granted only after a formalized request:

- In Rhineland-Palatinate, the web-based interface [MOGON OnDemand](#) simplifies access to the HPC cluster by [Allianz für Hochleistungsrechnen Rheinland-Pfalz \(AHRP\)](#). They allocate a certain percentage of the central computing capacity available at the universities of Mainz ([JGU](#)) and Kaiserslautern-Landau ([RPTU](#)) in a shared pool for scientists and researchers in Rhineland-Palatinate.
- The GWDG (Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung mbH Göttingen) provides [HPC resources](#) and [services](#) for researchers at local, regional, and national levels.

Bibliography

Burkhardt, Anne. "KI und Globale (Un)Gerechtigkeit: Ethische Perspektiven auf Künstliche Intelligenz." 2025, YouTube. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SL95cCn_nlY

Digital Humanities Climate Coalition. "Minimal Computing." 2025. GitHub. <https://sas-dhrh.github.io/dhcc-toolkit/toolkit/minimal-computing.html>

Executive Committee of the DFG. "Statement on the Influence of Generative Models of Text and Image Creation on Science and the Humanities and on the DFG's Funding Activities." 2023. <https://www.dfg.de/resource/blob/289676/89c03e7a7a8a024093602995974832f9/230921-statement-executive-committee-ki-ai-data.pdf>

Ferrer, Xavier, Tom van Nuenen, Jose M. Such, Mark Coté, and Natalia Criado. "Bias and Discrimination in AI: A Cross-Disciplinary Perspective." IEEE Technology and Society Magazine 40, no. 2 (2021): 72-80. [10.1109/MTS.2021.3056293](https://doi.org/10.1109/MTS.2021.3056293)

European Parliament and Council of the European Union. Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 March 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and amending certain Union legislative acts. OJ L 90, 15.3.2024, 2024. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1689/oj>

- Forschungsteam ZGKI. "EU AI ACT Kompass." 2025. <https://chatgpt.com/g/g-UOQ91wDRL-eu-ai-act-kompass-vom-zgki-wegweiser-fur-kmu-s>
- Ghent University. "GDPR: What Should I Take into Account When Developing or Using AI?" 2024. <https://onderzoektips.ugent.be/en/tips/00002164/>
- Leibniz Association. "Empfehlung zur Sicherung der guten wissenschaftlichen Praxis beim Umgang mit Künstlicher Intelligenz." 2024, Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/records/14420893>
- Li, Pengfei, Jianyi Yang, Mohammad A. Islam, and Shaolei Ren. "Making AI Less 'Thirsty': Uncovering and Addressing the Secret Water Footprint of AI Models." ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency, 2023. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2304.03271>
- Markert, Michael. "Entscheidungsbaum zu urheberrechtlichen Aspekten der Nutzung von Digitalisaten." Ver. 0.1, 2024. https://liascript.github.io/course/?https://api.allorigins.win/raw?url=https%3A%2F%2Fraw.githubusercontent.com%2FMichaelMarkert%2FSODa%2Fmain%2Fdocs%2Furhg_baum.md#1
- Mauermann, Johanna, and Sarah Oberbichler. "LLM Biases: Expected and Unexpected Model Design Effects in Historical Newspaper Article Extraction on the Messina Earthquake." 2025, DH Lab Blog, <https://dhlab.hypotheses.org/6060>
- Navigli, Roberto, Simone Conia, and Björn Ross. "Biases in Large Language Models: Origins, Inventory, and Discussion." Journal of Data and Information Quality 15, no. 2 (June 2023): Article 10. <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3597307>
- Oberbichler, Sarah. "AI Model Research Documentation Sheet (AIRDocS)." 2024, Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/records/14550113>

Platforms, Models, and Tools

- Allen Institute for AI. "Tülu 3." Accessed February 2025. <https://allenai.org/tulu>
- Allianz für Hochleistungsrechnen Rheinland-Pfalz (AHRP). Accessed February 2025. <https://www.ahrp.info/index.shtml>
- Anaconda. "Anaconda for Enterprise AI." Accessed February 2025. <https://www.anaconda.com/>
- "Awesome List LLMs." GitHub repository. Accessed February 2025. <https://github.com/Hannibal046/Awesome-LLM>
- "Carbon Footprint Calculator for Machine Learning." Accessed February 2025. <https://mlco2.github.io/impact/>
- ChatAI of GWDG. Accessed February 2025. <https://chat.gwdg.de/home>
- ChatGPT. Accessed February 2025. <https://chatgpt.com/>
- Claude. Accessed February 2025. <https://claude.ai/>
- Copilot. Accessed February 2025. <https://github.com/features/copilot>
- DeepL. Accessed February 2025. <https://www.deepl.com/de/translator>
- Detectron 2. GitHub repository. Accessed February 2025. <https://github.com/facebookresearch/detectron2>
- Elicit. Accessed February 2025. <https://elicit.com/?redirected=true>

- Google Cloud AI. Accessed February 2025. <https://cloud.google.com/ai/generative-ai?hl=de>
- Google Colab Notebooks. Accessed February 2025. <https://colab.research.google.com/>
- GPT4All. Accessed February 2025. <https://www.nomic.ai/gpt4all>
- Grammarly. Accessed February 2025. <https://www.grammarly.com/>
- GroqCloud. Accessed February 2025. <https://console.groq.com/playground>
- GWDG. "API Access." Accessed February 2025. <https://docs.hpc.gwdg.de/services/saia/index.html#api-request>
- GWDG. "HPC Resources." Accessed February 2025. <https://gwdg.de/hpc/>
- HuggingFace. Accessed February 2025. <https://huggingface.co/>
- HuggingFace. "Model Caracal." Accessed February 2025. <https://huggingface.co/spaces/wjbmattingly/caracal>
- LLM360. Accessed February 2025. <https://www.llm360.ai/>
- Meta AI. "Llama." Accessed February 2025. <https://www.llama.com/>
- MOGON OnDemand. Accessed February 2025. <https://mod.hpc.uni-mainz.de/pun/sys/dashboard/>
- Ollama. Accessed February 2025. <https://ollama.com/>
- OpenAI. "Deep Research." Accessed February 2025. <https://openai.com/index/introducing-deep-research/>
- ORKG Ask. Accessed February 2025. <https://orkg.org/>
- "Pandas AI." GitHub repository. Accessed February 2025. <https://github.com/sinaptik-ai/pandas-ai>
- Research Rabbit. Accessed February 2025. <https://www.researchrabbit.ai/>
- Semantic Scholar. Accessed February 2025. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/>
- Writefull. Accessed February 2025. <https://www.writefull.com/>